

Mechanism of radioprotection by β -aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide[†]

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β -Aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide (AET) undergoes tautomeric conversion to mercaptoethylguinidine (MEG) through a transient product in aqueous solution. This conversion is facilitated by increase of pH, concentration of AET and radiation dose upto 2.5 Gy. Analytical evidences indicate radiation protection mechanism offered by AET is due to formation of MEG and subsequent neutral radiolytic products. So long as these products contain SH and NH₂ groups separated by 2–3 carbon atoms, they are able to scavenge OH[•] radicals by proton donation from SH groups and absorption of H⁺ ions by NH₂ groups. These sulfhydryl compounds may block the peroxidation process by reacting with free radicals in competition with oxygen and may restore it to its original state.

β -Aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide (AET) is known to be a radioprotector and the radioprotective dose varies from 0.45 to 5 mM/kg depending upon biological specimens¹. The dose reduction factor (DRF) value varies from 1.00 to 1.34. It has been tried for better radioprotective efficacy at INMAS by combining with 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (HT). HT : AET concentration ratio of 90.82 : 14.23 μ M is maintained for different types of biological systems². Protection mechanism for this combination has been reported^{3–5}. Present study is an attempt to elucidate radiation-induced changes in AET that can be ascribed for its radioprotection aspect.

Results and Discussion

With the increase in concentration (from 10–100 μ g ml⁻¹) a consistent red-shift in the position of absorption maximum from 204 to 225 nm accompanied by sigmoidal increase in absorption intensity at absorption maximum occurred in the pH range 6.47–7.32. Mercaptoethylguinidine (MEG) obtained from AET on dissolution⁶ produced increasing amount of SH groups in addition to NH₂ and =NH chromophores present in AET. The presence of these auxochromes in increasing number is responsible for the red-shift⁷ and increase in intensity.

For 10 μ g ml⁻¹ of AET with increase in pH from 2.60 to 9.53, absorbance intensities at 210 and 215 nm increased. The conductance values were found to be high at alkaline pH. The isosbestic point was obtained at pH 5.54.

Tautomerisation of AET to MEG is facilitated by increase of pH. The uncharged and charged chromophores like SH, =NH, NH₃⁺ and NH₃⁺-C(=NH)NH are exposed in solution to the maximum extent at extreme alkaline pH values. At maximum pH values, charged species are maximum which results increase in conductance. At pH 5.54 these charged species get mutually neutralised³.

With increase in dose (dose rate 0.0123 Gy/s) for AET (concn. 10 μ g ml⁻¹), pH increased slightly up to 10 Gy but at higher doses upto 3000 Gy pH decreased. No change in absorbance intensity at 204 nm was observed up to 10 Gy but that at 230 nm (shoulder) it decreased from 0.26 (for unirradiated) to 0.18 (for 10 Gy) for AET. From 100 to 3000 Gy, neither absorption maximum at 204 nm nor shoulder at 230 nm were observed. The absorption maximum at 204 nm is stable up to 10 Gy. But as dose increased, the chromophores were damaged and at 3000 Gy complete disruption of chromophores occurred. Ammonia liberation with dose up to 10 Gy explains increase of pH.

Results of Table 1 indicate that at 2.5 Gy, C–S–C bond and alkane groups of AET were slowly disrupted. The S–C–N bond vibration could not be obtained even at 2.5 Gy dose. Unirradiated compound showed very small SH group vibration which became significant at 2.5 Gy. But at 10 Gy, only =NH and NH₂ group vibrations could be obtained⁸.

At a concentration of 4.3×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ of AET at pH 6.9 in N₂O saturated water, a transient absorption maxi-

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Table 1. IR spectral studies on AET*

γ_{\max} cm ⁻¹	% T	Assignment
Unirradiated		
633 (medium)	20	C-S-C
1425 (weak)	20	Alkane group
1583 (weak)	73	S-C-N
1650	40	=NH and -NH ₂
2790-2800 (s)	55	SH
Dose 2.5 Gy		
600-650	10	C-S-C
1425	10	Alkane group
1583	-	S-C-N does not exist
1650	35	=NH and -NH ₂
2770-2800	30	SH
Dose 10 Gy		
600-650	-	C-S-C bond disrupted
1425	-	Alkane groups disrupted
1583	-	S-C-N bond does not exist
1650	30	=NH and -NH ₂
2770-2800	-	SH does not exist

*Experiments were repeated thrice.

mum at 360 nm attributed to Br₂⁻ band was obtained by pulse radiolysis study. AET to MEG conversion intermediate was reported earlier⁵. The rate constant for the formation of (SCN)₂⁻ has been monitored at 500 nm. Assuming the rate constant of K_{SCN⁻ + OH[•]} = 1.1 × 10¹⁰ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, the rate constant for interaction of OH[•] radical with AET was found to be 3.3 × 10⁹ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹. The conversion of AET to MEG in aqueous solution is facilitated by increase of pH and radiation dose. The above conversion and hydroxyl radical induced radiolytic products and subsequent oxidation products have been reported earlier^{3,6}.

In the initial steps so long ammonia is liberated from AET, increase in pH was observed. With further increase in dose more of carboxylic groups have been formed. So decrease of pH took place. Up to 2.5 Gy, SH and NH₂ groups are present and these are separated by 2-3 carbon atoms. Proton donation from SH group for its reaction with hydroxyl radicals is an important step for radioprotection^{3,6}. But at 10 Gy, the compound gets disrupted to such an extent that no more radioprotection is possible⁸.

The decay of the absorption band at 360 nm for Br₂⁻ was considerably faster when AET was present, indicating that Br₂⁻ reacts with AET and the rate constant for this reaction is 1.04 × 10⁸ mol⁻¹ dm⁻³ s⁻¹. Overall rate constant for this reaction was determined using competition kinetic method and was faster by more than one order of magnitude than

the rate constant for the reaction of Br₂⁻ with AET. In the radiolysis of AET, OH[•] reacts predominantly with Br⁻ dissociated in aqueous solution, then undergoes further reaction with AET. Fraction of OH[•] would, however, undergo a direct reaction with the base AET. The various possibilities of OH[•] attack are shown in Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 1 contains radiolytic products which are still capable of interacting with hydrogen radical by NH₂ group, solvated electron by =NH₂⁺ group and OH[•] radical by NH₃ group. Moreover, if an organic molecule RH like AET under radiation is converted into a free radical R[•],

it may undergo radical-radical reaction, R[•] + R[•] → R₂ or peroxidation in presence of oxygen,

A protective agent PH such as sulfhydryl compound may block the peroxidation process by reacting with free radical in competition with oxygen and may restore the organic molecule to the original state,

Experimental

AET (m.w. 280.22; Sigma) m.p. 188° (lit. 190-196°), and EDTA (E. Merck) were used. Tripple-distilled water was used. Instruments : Cambridge CE 599 spectrophotometer; IR-Perkin-Elmer FTS 40, BIO-RAD; CM 82 T conductivity bridge; Gamma Cell 220 (Atomic Energy of Canada), dose rate determination by FBX dosimetry⁹; pH meter-Toshniwal CL 46.

Pulse radiolysis study was carried out with 7 MeV electrons of 50 ns pulse width, from a linear accelerator, and the transients were detected by kinetic spectrophotometry with optical path length of 1 cm, as described earlier^{10,11}. The absorbed dose was determined by aerated 0.01 mol dm⁻³ thiocyanate dosimeter having a $G(E)$ value of 2.23×10^{-4} m² J⁻¹ at 500 nm. The absorbed dose was kept at 7–8 Gy/pulse. Solutions were prepared in nanopure water from a Barnstead system.

From a stock solution of AET (100 μ g ml⁻¹) required concentrations were prepared. Experimental measurements of solutions in the unirradiated and differently irradiated states were made by respective instruments. AET solution (concentration 500 μ g ml⁻¹) was irradiated to 2.5 Gy or 10 Gy alongwith unirradiated sample. The solutions were lyophilised at –30° at 6 mbar pressure for 6 h, made pellets with KBr and then the IR spectra were taken.

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